

THE CASE STUDY METHOD: A MODERN TOOL FOR 21ST CENTURY CHEMISTRY TEACHER

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Annotation: *In the 21st century, education systems focus not only on imparting knowledge but also on developing students' ability to apply that knowledge in real-life situations, analyse information, make decisions and think critically. The case study method has emerged as a popular teaching approach in schools, offering an active and interactive learning experience. This article examines the theoretical basis of this method, how it is implemented in practice, and its advantages and challenges.*

Keywords: *case study, pedagogy, active learning, critical thinking, school practice, 21 century skills.*

Introduction. The rapid changes of the modern era present new challenges to education systems. Today's school students need to be able to make informed decisions in complex situations, defend their viewpoints and collaborate effectively in teams. Traditional, lecture-based teaching methods are no longer sufficient. Educators are seeking methods that enhance students' cognitive engagement and encourage independent learning. One such method is the case study approach.

This approach involves analysing real or hypothetical scenarios to encourage active learning. First introduced at Harvard Law School in the late 19th century, it later spread widely across various fields, including business, medicine, and pedagogy. In the field of pedagogy, the case study method is grounded in constructivist theory, which posits that learners develop knowledge through personal experiences. Rather than passively receiving information, students actively analyse issues, make decisions and draw conclusions. This method significantly contributes to the development of student's cognitive and social skills [1].

The case study method is effective in multiple school subjects. For instance:

- Chemistry and biology: discussions on environmental issues, laboratory safety incidents and ethical dilemmas in scientific research.

- History: multi-perspective analysis of historical events, identification of causes and consequences, and proposing alternative scenarios.

- Literature: analysis of characters' decisions and moral dilemmas.

- Civics and Law: an exploration of legal cases and social justice issues [3].

By analysing real-life cases, students can understand the practical relevance of theoretical knowledge, develop independent thinking skills, participate in discussions and learn how to make responsible decisions.

The following advantages and disadvantages of this method are noted in the literature [4-5]:

Advantages:

- Enhances critical thinking skills;
- Encourages active participation and teamwork;
- Connects theory with practice;
- Develops communication and analytical skills.

Challenges:

- Requires thorough preparation by the teacher;

- Demands sufficient time for discussion;
- Some students may struggle with open debates.

To overcome these challenges, teachers should provide clear guidelines, gradually increase task complexity, and offer support to boost students' confidence.

Methods and material. In recent years, numerous studies have been conducted to examine the effectiveness of the case-study method in various fields of education:

Bonney [6] investigated the application of the case-study method in teaching key biology concepts, including chemical bonds, osmosis, meiosis and mitosis, and DNA structure. The study included test questions related to the case-study materials, as well as control questions. Students scored 18% higher on the case-study-related questions than on the control questions (73% vs 60%). Furthermore, 82% of students found the case-study lessons useful, whereas lower percentages were observed for traditional methods (70% for stories and 58% for textbooks).

Mensah et.al [7] focused on teaching financial accounting to senior high school students using case studies. The experimental and control groups were compared, with the former receiving instruction via case studies. Post-test results showed that the average score in the experimental group increased by 4.81 points, raising it to 75.31. The effect size ($\eta^2 = 0.15$) revealed a notable enhancement in decision-making and critical thinking abilities.

Similarly, Sagitova et al. [8] conducted a study at Uzhhorod National University (Ukraine) with future teachers, examining the integration of the case-study method into teacher training programmes. Data collected through observation, interviews and surveys showed that this approach significantly improved professional competencies and motivation to learn.

Sadykov et.al [9] investigated the effectiveness of the case-study method in teaching chemistry to 9th-grade students. The study included a control group taught using traditional methods and an experimental group that completed case-study tasks. According to the results of the final tests, the experimental group demonstrated higher quality of learning (91.7%), achieving an average score of 11.75, whereas the control group achieved an average score of 10.08 and a percentage score of 58.3%. Additionally, survey results indicated that the case-study method increased students' interest in and engagement with chemistry learning (table 1).

Table 1. Comparative analysis of case study research findings

Author, Year	Purpose of the Study	Methods Used	Results
Bonney, 2015 (Journal of Microbiology & Biology Education)	Evaluate the effectiveness of the case-study method in teaching biology concepts (chemical bonding, osmosis, meiosis/mitosis, DNA structure)	Four different case studies were provided to students, and performance was assessed through tests that contained both case-related and control questions.	Students scored 18% higher (73% vs. 60%) on case-study-related questions compared to control questions. 82% found case-study lessons useful; stories were rated 70%, textbooks 58%.
Mensah et.al, 2024 (Cogent Arts & Humanities)	Assess the effectiveness of the case-study method in financial accounting education among senior high school students.	Experimental and control groups were taught using case-study and traditional methods respectively; post-test scores were analysed.	The experimental group improved by 4.81 points, achieving a 75.31 average. Effect size ($\eta^2 = 0.15$) indicated substantial improvement in decision-making and critical thinking skills.
Sagitova et. al., 2024 (Herald of	Investigate the impact of the case-study method on	Case-study method was implemented in teacher training	The method significantly improved professional competencies and

Uzhhorod University)	professional competence and learning motivation of pre-service teachers.	courses; data was collected through observation, interviews, and questionnaires.	enhanced students' learning motivation.
Sadykov, 2024) (Bulletin of E.A. Buketov Karaganda University – Pedagogy Series)	Evaluate the effectiveness of the case-study method in 9th-grade chemistry lessons.	9th grade students were divided into control (traditional method) and experimental (case-study method) groups; results were assessed via final testing and student surveys.	The experimental group showed a 91.7% success rate with a higher average score (11.75 vs. 10.08). Surveys indicated increased learning engagement and better subject comprehension.

Studies conducted across different disciplines and educational levels demonstrate that the case-study method effectively improves student engagement, comprehension, critical thinking skills, professional competence and motivation to learn.

The application of the case study method in chemistry lessons

At Daryn specialised school-lyceum-boarding school in Karaganda, the case study method was used in chemistry lessons. During one lesson, students were presented with the real-life incident of a methane gas explosion in Karaganda. They then worked on this emergency using the case study method. This approach enabled students to apply their theoretical knowledge to real-life situations, develop their analytical skills and gain a deeper understanding of issues related to responsibility and safety.

The lesson aimed to explain the structure and properties of methane within the context of alkanes, while also drawing attention to the importance and dangers of this gas in everyday life. Students were provided with information about the danger's methane gas poses to human life due to its flammability, explosiveness, tendency to spread in the air and lack of odour.

The students were asked several questions about the case.

- Where is methane gas used?
- In what situations could it lead to an explosion?
- What should be done to prevent danger?
- Why do you think this incident occurred?
- Can you relate the chemical properties and physical characteristics of methane gas to this incident?

The students were divided into small groups and asked to share their thoughts and hold discussions. Each group tried to substantiate their point of view with evidence. Many students cited the improper use of gas appliances, a failure to address malfunctions promptly, and the absence of a ventilation system as reasons for this situation. It was also noted that, due to methane gas being odourless, a person may not notice it spreading. Upon analysing the chemical properties of methane, the students said that it reacts with oxygen in the air, undergoing a combustion reaction which releases a large amount of heat and poses an explosion risk. They also concluded that the accumulation of gas in a closed room is very dangerous (table 2).

At the end of the lesson, the students were introduced to information about the rules for safely using household gas appliances in everyday life. A concrete example proved that methane gas can pose a great danger if used incorrectly, increasing the student's interest in and responsibility for this topic. The class analysed the situation, identified the violated safety rules, discussed the potential consequences, and developed improved preventive measures. The students reflected on the importance of attentiveness, responsibility, and strict adherence to laboratory safety protocols. This

real-life incident reinforced their theoretical knowledge, enhancing their critical thinking and problem-solving skills (figure 1).

Figure 1. The application of the case study method in chemistry lessons

Table 2. A short fragment of a lesson with Case-study

Time	Students actions	Resources
20 minutes	<p>Case study: 'Methane explosion in a mine in Karaganda' In 2023, a methane gas explosion occurred at the Kostenko mine in the Karaganda region. The mine is owned by the ArcelorMittal Temirtau company. Several miners were killed or injured as a result of the explosion. The incident raised concerns about industrial safety and worker protection and prompted a wider discussion about these issues. According to experts, the explosion was caused by the accumulation of methane gas and inadequate ventilation.</p> <p>Questions: For Group 1: What is methane, and why is it dangerous? Where and how is methane gas formed? For Group 2: Why does methane gas accumulate in mines? What safety measures should be taken to prevent explosions? For group 3: How could this incident affect industrial safety and workers' rights? If you were an engineer, what steps would you take to prevent such a situation?</p>	Presentation Internet Videos

Conclusion: The case study method is an effective teaching approach that meets the educational demands of the 21st century. By placing students in real-life situations, it enables them to apply their theoretical knowledge, analyse complex issues, and develop their practical problem-solving skills. At

the same time, it fosters essential competencies such as communication, collaboration, leadership, and ethical reasoning. During teaching practice, a real laboratory incident helped students to understand the importance of safety protocols, connect theory with practice and develop risk management skills for their future careers.

The case study approach encourages active participation from students of varying abilities, making it an inclusive, student-centred learning method. Although it requires thorough preparation by the teacher, the long-term benefits are significant. Students take on an active investigative role, developing adaptability and decision-making skills that are essential in a rapidly changing world. In an increasingly complex society, methods such as case studies prepare students for academic success, lifelong learning and responsible citizenship.

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